

Invest in Open
Infrastructure

Towards Open Research Infrastructure

Lessons, Gaps, and What Comes Next

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RINN & ORI Summer Event

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We work across the open research infrastructure ecosystem on the financial, operational, and governance foundations that allow infrastructure to survive and thrive.

Funders & partners

Are we ready to open yet?

Not just a technical question — a governance,
funding, and political one.

The answer depends on what "ready" means and
who gets to decide

Today: what the global landscape tells us, and
what it offers this moment in the Netherlands.

Also see State of Open
Infrastructure 2025

What do we mean by open infrastructure?

The shared research infrastructures needed to support open science.

Examples:
open access publication
platforms, archival and
preservation tools, repositories,
scientific data, computing
libraries & frameworks

Our focus is on the narrow set of
open-source solutions, systems,
and supports that facilitate the
creation and dissemination of
open research content and data.

OpenAlex

Crowded - and more fragile than it

looks

digital Preservation
Open Preservation Tools Registry (COPTR)

COPTR helps practitioners find tools needed for long term digital preservation tasks. It describes 610 tools and 36 workflows.

- Find a digital preservation tool using the **Tools Grid** (or by stage, function, content type or file format). Or watch this video to learn more.
- View digital preservation workflows
- Add a tool, or find out more about how you can get involved
- Add a workflow
- About COPTR, including how to Contact Us, how COPTR is structured and how to access COPTR data via the API.

NEW FOR JULY 2021: COPTR has been re-launched with new functionality. Find out all about it in this video

What Search & Compare About Infra Finder Add an Open Infrastructure Give Feedback Support Infra Finder

Relat

Share Copy Link

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- Supporting New Business Models and Policy Environments..... 29
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Infra Finder: Discover open infrastructures that meet your needs

Q Search 104 Solutions Sort by: Last Updated

Filters
Clear All Update Results

Solution Category

Open Attributes

Technical Attributes

Community Engagement

Policies

Business or Organizational Model

Hosting Options

Location
Anywhere

JHOVE

Open Preservation Foundation
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

JHOVE (the JSTOR/Harvard Object Validation Environment, pronounced "jove") is an extensible software framework for performing format identification, validation, and characterization of digital objects. Form...

Computing library

Digital preservation tool

Open API

Learn More Compare

RePEc

RePEc

Open bibliography for economics and connex sciences. Author authority provider. Citation analysis. Preprint dissemination. Institution authority provider. And more.

Discovery system

Index or directory

Open API

Learn More Compare

OpenCitations Thoth Open Metadata

FAIRsharing.org standards, databases, policies search through all content

SEARCH ADVANCED SEARCH LOGIN

STANDARDS DATABASES POLICIES COLLECTIONS ORGANISATIONS ADD CONTENT STATS

Databases

A registry of knowledgebases and repositories of data and other digital assets.

Search Q SEARCH ADVANCED SEARCH

Clear All Registry: Database Recommended: true

1 2 3 ... 11 12 13

Displaying 1 to 30 of 365.

WormBase

Registry

WormBase is an international consortium of biologists and computer scientists

Policy demand is rising. Infrastructure funding models are still catching up.

- **Who mandates, who sustains:** The funders require open science practices – project based funding rarely covers what comes after.
- **What gets funded:** New projects. Innovation. 45 open infrastructures in latest Open Science NL call (~€35M). Built, launched, pointed to by policy.
- **What doesn't:** Operations. Maintenance. Coordination. The ongoing costs of keeping infrastructure alive and usable post-initial funding

NL universities drop Web of Science

VU Amsterdam

Barcelona Declaration + >€100K renewal cost → redirected to open infra

Utrecht University

Moved to OpenAlex, The Lens as alternatives

TU Delft

Dropped WoS; directing community toward open tools

University of Twente

Ended negotiations unanimously

Shifting dependencies

2016

VSNU–Elsevier deal — Netherlands pioneers first major national read-and-publish agreement

2025

New deal signed: UNL, NFU, NWO-i, KNAW + 23 universities of applied sciences
100% OA publishing in eligible journals through Dec 2026

Now

WoS/Scopus dependencies still live — Scopus included in 2025 deal
Disintermediation of citation databases ≠ disintermediation of publishing

Next

Where do WoS cancellation savings go? Into open alternatives
or absorbed into general budgets?

Digital sovereignty & geopolitics

EU Parliament → Qwant

Switched from Google Search explicitly citing digital sovereignty (June 2026)

EDIC Digital Commons

France, Germany, Netherlands, Italy: first multi-government co-investment in open European tech as public good – focused on maintenance + adoption

For research infrastructure

Digital sovereignty is becoming a procurement and legitimacy lever
→ Use it in the case for coordinated open infrastructure investment

The screenshot shows the "Infra Finder" website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the "Invest in Open Infrastructure" logo and links for "About IOI", "What We Do", "Our Impact", "Infra Finder" (highlighted), "News & Updates", and a "Get Involved" button. Below this is a secondary navigation bar with "Search & Compare", "About Infra Finder", "Add an Open Infrastructure", "Give Feedback", and "Support Infra Finder". The main content area has a search bar with "107 Solutions" and a "Sort by: Title, A-Z" dropdown. On the left, there is a "Filters" sidebar with categories like "Solution Category", "Open Attributes", "Technical Attributes", "Community Engagement", "Policies", "Business or Organizational Model", "Hosting Options", and "Location". The main area displays three solution cards: "2i2c" (Code for Science and Society), "Academic Preservation Trust (APTrust)", and "Arches Heritage Data Management Platform". Each card includes a brief description, location, and a "Learn More" button.

TABLE 1.

Total funding, and counts of awards, funders, and OIs for all awards and for awards categorized as direct support, adjacent support, and adoption support

Note that not all awards had amount information, some had an amount of zero, and some we were not able to categorize.

	All awards	Direct support	Adjacent support	Adoption support
Total funding (USD)	\$551,379,853	\$191,744,420	\$339,711,539	\$2,135,014
Award count	641	178	433	11
Funder count	28	23	20	7
OI count	54	42	41	8

FIGURE 1A.

Distribution of all funding by super-category

FIGURE 1B.

Distribution of direct funding by category

Open \neq free

Framing as "cheaper" hurts, not helps

- Migration and transitions come at a cost (especially to do well, shift off proprietary)
- Operating costs are real + often less visible if absorbed into institutional overhead
 - Staffing, hosting, maintenance, training, governance, curation, community support
- Cost considerations for global collaboration
- Costs shift, benefits of transparency and autonomy (not reduction in service, quality)

€35M / 45 projects

Open Science NL (Dec 2025) — largest round yet; BROCCOLI + DURF among them

NWO project model

Big grants: ~€1M over 4 years. TDCC model: 10 years innovation funding.
But what happens in year 5 / year 11?

SPII

UNL + SURF mapping what infrastructure universities actually need
Demand-side work before supply — rare and valuable

Philanthropy gap

Foundation funding for research infrastructure is not as prevalent as in the US
Public co-investment + institutional membership carry a heavier load, even amidst cuts

"We can't just assume [insert organisation here] will host forever"

Single points of reliance, seldom infinite backstops — diversified models needed

What's working + what it teaches us

- **Barcelona Declaration Network**

Multiple WoS/Scopus cancellations in 2025; open metadata as default

- **SURF cooperative**

100+ member institutions, legally structured, explicit coordination mandate

- **UNL/SURF/SPII**

Demand-side coordination, asking what universities need before building more supply

- **BROCCOLI**

National ORI hub, unanimous rector endorsement, feeds into OpenAIRE Graph - a federated, sovereignty-aligned model

1

Invest in governance and community feedback mechanisms

Document decisions, build review mechanisms, name the sunseting path — before year 4

2

Name the real costs

Map what scale costs — staff, hosting, curation, governance — and put it in front of funders early

3

Redirect disintermediation savings deliberately

WoS cancellation fees should flow to open alternatives. Require explicit institutional policy.

4

Resist the proliferation pull

Before building new, ask whether existing infra needs better support. Coordinate investment.

5

Diversify, diversify, diversify (or plan to)

Build institutional membership + national co-investment + EOSC linkage — not single-actor dependency

**Open research infrastructure
is not a niche concern –
it's a strategic bet on who
gets to know what, and on
whose terms.**

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Thank you

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